

MicroRNA Modulation of Regenerative Factors in Nucleus Pulposus Cells of the Intervertebral Disc

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INTRODUCTION:

In recent years the delivery of microRNAs (miRs) has gained traction as a method for improving tissue regeneration. Delivery of these short, non-coding, nucleic acids would bypass the drawbacks found in previous clinical trials involving growth factors, namely the associated short half-life and need for repeat injections [1]. Here miRs -140-5p mimic, -149-5p mimic, and -221-3p inhibitor were identified from the literature as having the potential to modulate regeneration of the IVD and stimulate rejuvenation of the nucleus pulposus (NP) cell phenotype and investigated in a rat NP 2D culture model. In parallel, non-viral cell penetrating peptides (CPPs)- cationic 30mer amphipathic peptide (RALA) [2] and GAG-binding enhanced transduction FGF2B-LK15-8R (GET-FLR) [3] were investigated to identify the most efficacious delivery vector for miR complexation and transfection of NP cells, with Lipofectamine RNAiMAX [4] serving as a positive control. The aim of this study was to screen miRs associated with increased matrix deposition rates as well as decreasing the expression of inflammatory response elements

METHODS:

Rat NP cells were isolated from donors following euthanasia and digested with collagenase type II and pronase, and culture expanded up to passage 3. Carrier-miR complexes were prepared with miRs -140, -149, and -221 inhibitor for RALA, GET-FLR, and Lipofectamine at optimal charge ratios. Following culture for three days transfected cells were fixed for protein expression quantification employing immunofluorescence, with antibody staining for regenerative matrix proteins: *ACAN*, *COL2*, and *SOX9*, and matrix degradative proteins: *ADAMTS-4*, *ADAMTS-5*, and *MMP-13*. Mean fluorescence intensity was quantified using a custom pipeline in CellProfiler 4.2.1, with normalisation to the non-transfected groups. All experiments were carried out in triplicate with differences between groups assessed by ordinary one-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparisons test using GraphPad Prism 9.4.0, with p values <0.05 considered to be significant.

RESULTS:

Transfection with miRs-140, -149, and -221 inhibitor resulted in significant increases in discogenic proteins in a 2D model. miR-140 led to a significant increase in expression of regenerative factors *ACAN*, *COL2*, and *SOX9* (Figure 1A & B). Protein expression of *ACAN* and *SOX9* was significantly increased following transfection with miR-149 (Figure 1C & D). miR-221 inhibitor enhanced the expression of *ACAN* and *COL2* to a significant degree (Figure 1E & F).

DISCUSSION:

This initial screening of miRs with regenerative potential in the IVD provides a framework for future investigations on the capabilities of miRs to modulate IVD renewal. This foundation can be used to develop high throughput experiments, enabling comparison of the functionality and therapeutic potential of miRs to better elucidate suitable miR candidates for progression to 3D culture models and *in vivo* studies, which better recapitulate the environment within the disc. Paired with the use of these more relevant models, insults such as cytokine induction could be utilised to represent the inflammatory milieu within a degenerative disc. Leading from this, potential strategies of resident NP cell renewal in the IVD can be investigated, with the aim of developing minimally invasive injectable therapeutics utilising miR platform technology.

SIGNIFICANCE:

miR delivery as a mode of tissue regeneration has garnered growing interest. Consequently, screening of miRs with renewal capacity is required prior to further studies in 3D or *in vivo*, as demonstrated here in a 2D culture model. However, further work is required to determine the beneficial effects of miR delivery when subjected to physiologically relevant microenvironmental conditions.

REFERENCES:

[1] Tsekoura *et al*, "Biomaterials to Facilitate Delivery of RNA Agents in Bone Regeneration and Repair", *ACS Biomaterials Science & Engineering*, 3(7): 1195-1206, 2017 [2] Raftery *et al*, "Highly versatile cell-penetrating peptide loaded scaffold for efficient and localised gene delivery to multiple cell types: From development to application in tissue engineering." *Biomaterials*, 216: 119277, 2019 [3] Blokpoel Ferreras *et al*, "Rapidly Transducing and Spatially Localized Magnetofection Using Peptide-Mediated Non-Viral Gene Delivery Based on Iron Oxide Nanoparticles". *ACS Applied. Nano Materials*, 4, 167-181, 2021 [4] Cardarelli *et al*, "The intracellular trafficking mechanism of Lipofectamine-based transfection reagents and its implication for gene delivery." *Scientific Reports* 6, 2016

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Figure 1: Representative images and relevant protein quantification demonstrating upregulation of regenerative proteins following transfection with miR-140-5p mimic (A & B), miR-149-3p mimic (C & D), and miR-221 inhibitor (E & F). NT: Non-transfected; LIPO: Lipofectamine. * p <0.05, ** p <0.01, *** p <0.001